

Table 2. Summary of measurement of sleep quality and cardiovascular among healthcare shift workers of the included studies.

Author (Country)	Sample size(n)	Exposure of working shift	Cardiovascular measures	Sleep quality measures	Outcome	Conclusions
Lajoie P. ³³ , 2015 (Canada)	Shift female hospital employees (n=121)	Rotating 12-hour day/night shifts	Metabolic syndrome	PSQI -sleep latency -sleep efficiency	<p>CVS result: Rotating 12-hour shift work was associated with two-fold increased risk of metabolic syndrome (OR=2.29) among female hospital workers.</p> <p>Sleep result:</p> <p>Night shift workers had significant poor sleep quality than day workers with 47.9% scoring > 5 on the PSQI compared to 32.7% of day workers (p < 0.01). They also reported poor sleep latency (42% vs 27%) and lower sleep efficiency indicating reduced sleep quality.</p>	Shift work strongly associated with metabolic syndrome among female workers however sleep quality was not a significant mediator and no significant association with metabolic syndrome.
Silva-Costa A ³² , 2015 (Brazil)	Night shift nurses (n = 340)	Work night shifts at least once a week or four times per month	Self-reported physician diagnosed cardiovascular disease: hypertension, coronary disease, myocardial infarction, or heart failure	Insomnia	<p>CVS result: The proportion of self-reported physician diagnosed CVD was 18% among day workers and 21% among night workers.</p> <p>Sleep result: The prevalence among night workers reported that 24% had nocturnal insomnia, 35% had diurnal insomnia, 13% experienced both while 23% of day workers reported nocturnal insomnia.</p>	Night workers who had insomnia during both sleep episodes had three times higher odds of developing cardiovascular disease compared to those without insomnia

Table 2 (continued). Summary of measurement of sleep quality and cardiovascular among healthcare shift workers of the included studies.

Author	Sample size(<i>n</i>)	Exposure of working shift	Cardiovascular measures	Sleep quality measures	Outcome	Conclusions
Hsu HC ³⁰ . 2021 (Taiwan)	393 Female work nurses	shift Not stated	Heart rate variability (HRV): TP, LF, HF, LF/HF, SDNN, RMSSD	PSQI	CVS result: Reduced autonomic function (lower TP) and higher mean heart rate are moderately predictive of poor sleep quality. Lower low frequency and total power and higher high frequency showed an altered autonomic balance. Sleep result: 95.9% had poor sleep quality with scoring 10.2. Majority had sleep efficiency less than 85% and 2.8% reported no difficulty falling back asleep after waking.	Poor sleep quality correlated with lower TP and LF. Poor sleep-in nurses is linked to autonomic imbalance, potentially elevating cardiovascular risk.
Panwar A ²⁹ . 2024 (India)	38 female nurses	Morning (9a.m. to 2p.m.) shift and night shift (9p.m.-9a.m.)	HRV: frequency and time domains	PSQI	CVS result: Decrease in standard deviation of normal-to-normal intervals, total power and high frequency power while increased in LF/HF ratio. Sleep result: Night shift nurses had significant poor sleep quality than morning shift nurses.	Night shift work is related to poor sleep quality and significant disruptions of heart rate variability.
Liao YH ³¹ . 2025 (Taiwan)	64 shift-work nurses (Intervention group: 32; Control group: 32)	4-week shift work schedule in the last 6 months (day, evening, night shift) LLLT using red and near-infrared light, administered three times a week for one month	Heart rate variability	Insomnia Severity Index	CVS result: No significant difference between in HRV outcomes. Sleep result: Intervention group resulted 4.3, controls 12.6 ($p < 0.001$), reflecting significantly less severe insomnia in the LED-LLLT group.	LLLT was effective in improving in shift-work nurses with insomnia. However, it did not have significant changes in heart rate variability.

Abbreviations: Cardiovascular (CVS); cardiovascular disease (CVD); Low frequency/high frequency (LF/HF); Heart rate variability (HRV); Total power (TP); Low frequency (LF); High frequency (HF); Standard Deviation of NN intervals (SDNN); Root Mean Square of Successive Differences (RMSSD); Low-level LED light therapy (LLLT)